

Confirmatory Factor Analyses (CFA) of Green Marketing Strategies on Marketing Performance the Mediating Role of Competitive Advantage: A Case of Small and Medium (SME) in Ethiopia

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Abstract – The aim of this study that provides, a conceptual linear Regression Model that introduction to analyses a Confirmatory Factor Analyses (CFA) of Green Marketing Strategies on Marketing Performance the Mediating role of Competitive Advantage: A case of SEM Ethiopia, and to discuss the concepts of Confirmatory factor data analysis, to construct Composite Reliability, Convergent Validity and to Confirm (SEM) Structural Equation Modeling practice Maintain Regression Weights be a Direct influence, indirect influence, and the indexed of mediation result to be providing based on our perspective on certain analysis, and the overall the mediating variable data analysis to be interpreting the Regression group Weights analyses in a model that includes, a Green Marketing Strategies like Green Product, Green Price, Green Place and Green Promotion that affect Marketing Performance a Mediating influence of Competitive Advantage, Innovational Orientation that affect MO and to analyses construct SEM, and to investigate with SPSS model V.25 that uses data from the Green Marketing strategies to analyse it's effect with Marketing Performance with mediating role of Competitive Advantage by using 380 sample respondents in Small and medium Enterprise, in Ethiopia.

Keywords: Green Product, Green Price, Green Place, Green Promotion Green Marketing, and Marketing Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dr. Najla Younis Mohammed Al-Murad (2022), Superfluous utilization of environmental market assets, precarious economic expansion, and most importantly, changes in climate characterize the modern age, of market as shift in consumer behaviour has an effect on green company reactions in this condition, and the green environmental economy is advocated around the globe as a method to stimulate economic growth, and it improve general societal welfare while also protecting the environment, phrases like eco-friendly recyclable materials, green products, green price, green, place, Green Promotion and ozone-friendly have become popular strategies among consumers behavior to expand the research activity.

The Green movement for green marketing has risen among organizations, and that want to stay ahead of the competition of the business that reflect in their various sectors, because of the sense of significant importance that customers identify with green concepts (Karunarathna et al., 2020), and that end of the businesses, and the organizations are adopting green marketing strategies of the firms and companies have embraced green marketing for a variety of purposes, including, among other things, to boost their revenue

and profits (Mukonza & Swarts, 2020), and a Green marketing, that they argue it is still in its early stages, and further research is required, (Hasan and Ali, 2015).

Green marketing strategies has have been shown to improve the performance in the latest business and Green researches, (Eneizan et al., 2016; Setyawati et al., 2020), nonetheless, we discovered at a very little research has to be looked into green marketing strategies of the business and environmental in terms of organizations, and in fact, the business organizations has distinctive characteristics from a large company or other types of business, and it considering the competitive advantage of the strategies of a continuing strategic aim, looking at from the perspective of a strategic green marketing strategic plan that poses a significant, and to void in the literature, and opportunity, that to give a complete knowledge of the convergence of green marketing strategies and market performance, and competitive advantage of a robust theoretical strategies is to be essential.

As a result, in order to fill this vacuum of green environment and the current investigation looked at the influence of green marketing strategies on small organizations' competitive advantage strategies and, marketing performance.

The study goals are to see, how the green marketing mix strategies that affect marketing performance the mediating role of competitive advantage in small and Medium organizations, of Ethiopia, and the research is structured and designed in the following way, and a detailed research analysis on green marketing strategies like Green product, Green Price, Green Place, Green Promotion for the contribution of market success, competitive advantage with Marketing Performance, as well as the research investigation framework, theories, research analytical methodologies, methods of analysis of data, and findings and summaries, and all included in the discussion. Eventually, in the concluding remarks, there is a review of the consequences and alternate investigation pathways to investigate SEM designed and to Construct Convergent Validity and to Constructs Composite Reliability for the contribution of Green Marketing Strategies, in Ethiopia, Africa.

2. CONCEPTUAL INVESTIGATION

Fig -1: Investigation Framework

Source: AMOS Output (2023)

3. INVESTIGATION APPROACH AND DESIGN

A Deductive research Philosophy, Quantitative research approach the quantitative approach will be served research in many ways and the justifications support why quantitative approach will be selected forth is research most of the empirical investigations in Small and Medium Enterprise in Ethiopia, has to be conducted by adopting quantitative approach in their designs to determine an expected relationships which might emerge from interaction between a set of given research variables, and this approach that has to be designed Confirmatory research designed that has Structural Equation Modeling to be developed the **mediation** variable of Competitive advantage that affect Marketing Performance of Small and Medium enterprises of Ethiopia, and data has designed to construct Composite Reliability and Convergent Face to face Validity Regression group model that has to be analysed, direct effect, indirect Effect, Blanco-Donoso, L. (2019), and there are indirect and direct effects. We have shown that the indirect effect, with the evidence of, and feelings through identification in the first-person, but not the third-person narrative voice condition to designed, Hayes, A. F. (2022), with Ethiopian Industrial park, Federal Construction office, Coffee trading and Factory PLC, and data collected from 380 Respondents, and Research technique to be designed with Simple random techniques and Stratified sampling technique has to be designed in Oromia Regional state West Guji zone Coffee trading and Factory Knoster, K. C., & Goodboy, A. K. (2020).

4. CONSTRUCT VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY STUDY OF THE STRATEGY

Table -1: Convergent Validity and Reliability of the Variables

Variables	Construct Item			Loading Factors	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Green Product	PROD3	<---	GPROD	.677	.847	.839	.578
	PROD2	<---	GPROD	.809			
	PROD1	<---	GPROD	.788			
Green Price	PRIC3	<---	GPRICE	.768	.853	.850	.594
	PRIC2	<---	GPRICE	.793			
	PRIC1	<---	GPRICE	.751			
Green Place	PLACE3	<---	GPLACE	.787	.924	.923	.526
	PLACE2	<---	GPLACE	.754			
	PLACE1	<---	GPLACE	.624			
Green Promotion	PROM4	<---	GPROD	.621	.928	.932	.498
	PROM3	<---	GPROD	.770			
	PROM2	<---	GPROD	.764			
	PROM1	<---	GPROD	.659			
Competitive Advantage	COMP1	<---	COMP	.658	.867	.865	.596
	COMP2	<---	COMP	.989			

	COM3	<---	COMP	.663			
	COMP4	<---	COMP	.731			
Marketing Performance	MARP1	<---	MARKP	.602	.838	.841	.545
	MARP2	<---	MARKP	.875			
	MARP3	<---	MARKP	.854			
	MARP4	<---	MARKP	.812			
	MARP5	<---	MARKP	.986			

Source: AMOS Output (2023)

Face to face Convergent validity, which has to be described, and construct Convergent validity subgroups, and it has to be is evaluated that has ensure that the measurement model is accurately fit, and it has to be determine the proportion of the total variance indicated by metrics for calculation of measurement errors using Green Product (.578), Green Price (.594), Green Place (.526), Green Promotion (.498), Competitive Advantage(.596), and Marketing Performance (.545) the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) result square root of loading factors of Confirmatory Factor analyses without Green promotion all Measurement model error are highly fit AVE output to construct Convergent Validity result is morethan 0.5% has to be accept.

As per the SEM review (Hair et al., 2017), the minimum value proposed Composite reliability level is 0.7, and the AVE level of 0.5, is the minimum acceptable level that has to show in Table 1 and Fig. 2, Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability are used to assess in every dimension internal consistency reliability, and when the alpha coefficient of any component of a building surpasses 0.7, the items are regarded as extremely reliable (Gada Gizachew Wakjira and Shashi Kanti, 2022), and it using internal Consistence of Composite Reliability result that shows Green Product (.839), Green Price (.850), Green Place (.923), Green Promotion (.932), Competitive Advantage(.865), and Marketing Performance (.841) output of Composite reliability, the assumption of Cronbach’s alpha coefficients result shows in both construct variable are morethan 0.70% of the individual structures the products were regarded as exceptionally precise between Composite reliability and Cronbach alpha measure has rare difference to construct the Measurement model, based on the above assumption the model has to be valid(Hair Jr. et al., 2017).

Fig -2: CONSTRUCT VALIDITY
Source: AMOS Output (2023)

5. EVALUATING HYPOTHESES TESTING

Table -2: Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

	Variables		Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Decision
H1:	COMP	<---	GPROD	.039	.061	1.642	.521	Unsupported
H2:	COMP	<---	GPRICE	.206	.067	3.059	.002	Supported
H3:	COMP	<---	GPLACE	.037	.075	.488	.005	Supported
H4:	COMP	<---	GPRO	.123	.083	1.473	.001	Supported
H5:	MARKP	<---	GPROD	.004	.009	.397	.691	Unsupported
H6:	MARKP	<---	GPRICE	.022	.010	2.142	***	Supported
H7:	MARKP	<---	GPLACE	.003	.013	1.235	.015	Supported
H8:	MARKP	<---	GPRO	.015	.013	1.138	.055	Supported
H9:	MARKP	<---	COMP	.696	.097	7.197	***	Supported

Source: AMOS Output (2023)

To analyze the study hypotheses testing by calculating the path coefficient is the final stage in assessing the structural Equation model (SEM), and the lower Proportional Value (p-value), the stronger the association (Hair et al., 2017). Table displays the structural model's direct Association results, including the connection between hypotheses to be tested from H1 to H9 to be constructed to support the Effect of Green Marketing mix strategies on Marketing performance the Mediating role of Competitive advantage of SME, Ethiopia.

Based on designed the data to calculate and estimated statistical significance for every, independent variables of Green Marketing mix strategies, from Mediating Variables of Competitive advantage, and

dependent variable of Marketing Performance is significant information supplied, and the values of t and p indicates whether the regression weight coefficients of the variables in the population data output result that indicated Relationship between Green Product and Competitive Advantage (.521**), Relationship between Green Price and Competitive Advantage (.002**), relationship between Green Distribution and Competitive advantage (.005**), relationship between Green Promotion and Competitive Advantage (.001**), relationship between Green Product and Market Performance (.691**), the relationship between Green Price and Market Performance (.000**), relationship between Green Promotion and Market Performance (.015**), the relationship between Green place and Marketing Performance (.055**) and relationship between Competitive Advantage and Market Performance (.000**) value of Regression weight result are constructed.

Based on the assumption output result that indicated that to infer that the independent variables output of Marketing Mix Strategies between Green Product with Competitive Advantage and between Green Product mix, and Marketing Performance that means H1 and H5 has to be Unsupported result the Alternative Hypotheses are accepted and Negative result it shows are statistically insignificant with p-Value result is higher than >0.05, and the remaining H2, H3, H4, H6, H7, H8 and H9 result are supported result, the Null hypotheses of regression weight is rejected, and the Alternative Hypotheses is Accepted it indicated a positive output that shows are statistically significant the p-Value result that shows less than < 0.005%. In our situation, the table shows that all independent variables possess a positive influence and that all independent variable's p-values are less than 0.05 based on this assumption.

H1: There is a negative and insignificant relationship between Green Product with Competitive Advantage as an intermediate variable.

H2: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Price with Competitive Advantage.

H3: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Distribution with Competitive Advantage as an intermediate variable.

H4: There is a Negative insignificant relationship between Green Promotion with Competitive Advantage as an intermediate variable.

H5: There is a positive and significant relationship between Green Product with Marketing Performance.

H6: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Price with Marketing Performance

H7: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Distribution with Marketing Performance.

H8: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Promotion with Market Performance.

H9: There is a positive significant relationship between Competitive Advantage with Market Performance.

6. CONSTRUCT MEASUREMENT MODEL OF THE STRATEGY

Table -3: Measurement Model Hypotheses Testing

	Variables		Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Decision
H1a:	PROD2	<---	GPROD	1.352	.163	8.290	***	Supported
H2a:	PROD1	<---	GPROD	.973	.117	8.308	***	Supported
H3a:	PRIC3	<---	GPRICE	.653	.234	4.675	***	Supported

H4a:	PRIC2	<---	GPRICE	1.196	.121	9.849	***	Supported
H5a:	PRIC1	<---	GPRICE	.716	.097	7.395	***	Supported
H6a:	PLACE3	<---	GPLACE	.323	.098	7.904	***	Supported
H7a:	PLACE2	<---	GPLACE	.944	.076	2.490	***	Supported
H8a:	PLACE1	<---	GPLACE	.727	.079	9.256	***	Supported
H9a:	PROM4	<---	GPROD	.324	.654	1.966	***	Supported
H10a:	PROM3	<---	GPROD	1.160	.101	1.462	***	Supported
H11a:	PROM2	<---	GPROD	1.239	.109	1.411	***	Supported
H12a:	PROM1	<---	GPROD	.814	.089	9.100	***	Supported
H13a:	COMP1	<---	COMP	.476	.345	9.987	***	Supported
H14a:	COMP2	<---	COMP	1.586	.121	3.074	***	Supported
H15a:	COMP3	<---	COMP	1.010	.078	2.941	***	Supported
H16a:	COMP4	<---	COMP	.830	.093	8.969	***	Supported
H17a:	MARP1	<---	MARKP	.876	.124	5.876	***	Supported
H18a:	MARP2	<---	MARKP	.871	.106	8.234	***	Supported
H19a:	MARP3	<---	MARKP	1.109	.130	8.519	***	Supported
H20a:	MARP4	<---	MARKP	1.041	.139	7.481	***	Supported
H21a:	MARP5	<---	MARKP	2.290	.267	8.577	***	Supported

Source: AMOS Output (2023)

The Measurement model that regression result based on the assumption of Green Marketing Mix Strategies of Green Product, Green Price, Green Place, Green Promotion, with Competitive advantage, Green Product, Green Price, Green Place, Green Promotion, with Marketing Performance measurement variables result that shows the positive relationship influence the Null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative Measurement model result output are highly Supported the p-Value result of both predicted measurement model result is <0.05, it indicates supported hypotheses result of the date, based on this assumption the judgment of hypotheses of Regression weight model can be drawn that there has been a significant and positive influence, and we dismiss our false assertions while supporting the hypotheses.

H1a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Product with Green Product 2

H2a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Product and Green Product 1

H3a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Price with Green Price 3

H4a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Price and Green Price 2

H5a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Price and Green Price 1.

H6a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green place and Green place2.

H7a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green place and Green place1.

H8a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Product and Green Promotion 4

H9a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Product and Green Promotion 3

H10: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Product affecting the Green Promotion 2

H11a: There is a positive significant relationship between Green Product affecting the Green Promotion 1

H12a: There is a positive significant relationship between Competitive advantage has indirectly affecting via Competitive Advantage 1 as an intermediate variable.

H13a: There is a positive significant relationship between Competitive advantage has indirectly affecting the Market Performance via Competitive Advantage 2 as an intermediate variable.

H14a: There is a positive significant relationship between Competitive advantage has indirectly affecting the via Competitive Advantage 3 as an intermediate variable.

H15a: There is a positive significant relationship between Competitive advantage has indirectly affecting the Competitive Advantage 4 as an intermediate variable.

H16a: There is a positive significant relationship between marketing performance has directly affecting the Market Performance 1.

H17a: There is a positive significant relationship between marketing performance has directly affecting the Market Performance 2.

H18a: There is a positive significant relationship between marketing performance has directly affecting the Market Performance 3.

H19a: There is a positive significant relationship between marketing performance has directly affecting the Market Performance 4.

H20a: There is a positive significant relationship between marketing performance has directly affecting the Market Performance 5.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Face to face Convergent validity, which has to be described, and construct Convergent validity subgroups, and it has to be is evaluated that has ensure that the measurement model is accurately fit, and it has to be determine the proportion of the total variance indicated by metrics for calculation of measurement errors using Green Product (.578), Green Price (.594), Green Place (.526), Green Promotion (.498), Competitive Advantage(.596), and Marketing Performance (.545) the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) result square root of loading factors of Confirmatory Factor analyses without Green promotion all Measurement model error are highly fit AVE output to construct Convergent Validity result is morethan 0.5% has to be accept.

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RECOMMENDATIONS

It gives the results of this research, the recommendations of the study are constructed, and the SEM of Marketing Performance management practice in the manufacturing sector of SME in Ethiopia should implement effective marketing mix strategies to help them gain a mediating role of competitive advantage over their competitors, the assumption of market performance to be improves.

Organizations in the manufacturing sector of SME should focused on the available resources are formulating the marketing mix strategies component for marketing effectiveness of Green Marketing, Green price, Green, Place and Green Promotion strategies with mediating factor of competitive advantage, organizations must develop customer-focused green Marketing strategies are also improve.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The Authors to be contributed to the text, methods of data collection, data analysis, and research evaluation, as well as reading, and final manuscript approval.

In addition, both writers affirm that the agreement must be made responsible for all aspects of work in ensuring, and to adequate investigation and research resolution of questions relating to the quality or credibility of any part of the work in future study of the investigation.

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